

ASSESSING THE CONTRIBUTION OF OPTICAL AND SAR DATA FOR FRACTIONAL SAVANNAH WOODY VEGETATION MAPPING

C. Karakizi¹, O. Gounari², E. Sofikiti², G. Begkos², K. Karantzalos², E. Symeonakis¹

¹Department of Natural Sciences, Manchester Metropolitan University, Manchester, M1 5GD, UK – c.karakizi@mmu.ac.uk

²Remote Sensing Laboratory, National Technical University of Athens, 15780 Zographos, Greece

ABSTRACT

Savannahs are under threat from land degradation, not least due to woody vegetation encroachment. Here, we target the accurate high-resolution mapping of fractional woody vegetation cover in a South African savannah region, and assess the contribution of optical (Sentinel-2, S2), radar (Sentinel-1, S1) and ancillary data (bioclimatic and soils). Firstly, we created fractional woody cover (FCW) samples based on very high resolution satellite imagery and then we performed several regression experiments using different combinations of S1, S2 and auxiliary data temporal metrics for both dry and wet seasons. Highest regression rates of over 80% were documented for the all-data and all-season combined experiments, while S2 only models clearly outperformed the S1 ones. An interesting outcome from the results analysis was that appending ancillary bioclimatic and soils information to the S2-based experiments was proven to be more effective than the inclusion of S1 metrics.

Index Terms— Sentinel-2, Sentinel-1, Bush Encroachment, South Africa, Random Forest Regression

1. INTRODUCTION

Drylands cover approximately 40% of the land surface of the Earth and support roughly one-third of the global human population. The savanna biome in particular covers 50% of the African continent and 20% of the global land surface, while also representing around a third of terrestrial net primary production, and comprising a critical regulating component of the land carbon sink [1]. Over the last decades, savannahs have been under pressure from human activities, exacerbated by climate change, with dramatic shifts in vegetation distribution and, consequently, alterations of their function, threatening the ecosystem services provided to some of the continent's most vulnerable populations [2]. Therefore, monitoring the process and evolution of land degradation in these ecosystems is considered of great importance for the scientific community, regional and national governments, as well as international organizations and institutions, such as the United Nations Convention to Combat Decertification (UNCCD).

Land degradation in savannahs has often been associated with the encroachment or densification of its woody component at the expense of grasses [1], [3]. To this end, a number of recent studies focus their research in monitoring and mapping woody vegetation using satellite imagery [4], [5]. However, savannah patchy and discontinuous nature has rendered its accurate mapping a challenging task, especially since most studies up to now have employed medium resolution imagery, such as Landsat with a pixel size of 30m. The launch of the Sentinel-1 (S1) and Sentinel-2 (S2) satellites has instigated a significant increase of interest in higher resolution mapping for various vegetation mapping applications [5], [6]. Towards this end, in this paper we target accurate fractional woody cover (FCW) mapping in a South African savannah region, while assessing different experimental set-ups of freely-available S2, S1 and ancillary bioclimatic and soils data.

2. MATERIALS & METHODS

2.1. Study Area

The study area is located in the Kagisano-Molopo local municipality in the Northwest Province of South Africa and covers an area of approx. 15,000 km². It is a hot, semi-arid steppe which receives most rainfall during the warmer summer months from October to March. The average midday temperatures range from 18°C in June to 31°C in January. The region is the coldest during June when the temperature drops to 0°C on average at night. The average rainfall per annum is ~450mm [7]. The whole study area falls within the Savannah Biome dominated by the Molopo Bushveld vegetation type [8]. Other vegetation types include Ghaap Plateau Vaalbosveld, Kuruman Mountain Bushveld, Mafikeng Bushveld, Southern Kalahari Salt Pans and Stella Bushveld [7].

2.2. Training Data

Training data were created based on the open-access, very high resolution (VHR) RGB satellite data of the ESRI World Imagery (EWI) layer. For our area of study, the EWI data were acquired between 2019 and 2022 and have a

spatial resolution of 0.6 m. In order to create training samples of woody cover fractions, we firstly manually annotated 3,500 points on the EWI layer in three classes: woody vegetation, non-woody vegetation, and non-vegetation. We used these annotations to train Random Forest (RF) and Support Vector Machines (SVM) classifiers, employing the RGB bands of the ESRI layer, as well as, an additional band we calculated based on the visible vegetation index formula [4], [9]. The RF and SVM models were then used to generate predictions for an area of 50x50 0.6m EWI pixels (i.e., 30x30m), centered on each of the 3,500 points.

The accuracy of the classification predictions was assessed by holding out a 40% dataset for testing. User's and producer's accuracy rates for the woody vegetation class were calculated at 93.5% and 95.3% with the RF classifier, and at 94.5% and 95.7% for the SVM, respectively. Better performance for the SVM classifier was also supported by a thorough visual assessment on the produced prediction masks, and so the SVM predictions were selected in order to generate FWC samples at 10m resolution. In particular, nine (3x3) 10m samples of FWC were calculated for each 30x30m prediction, as the percentage of pixels classified as woody vegetation at the equivalent 10x10m S2 pixel footprint. This resulted in 31,500 FWC samples at 10m spatial resolution.

2.3. Sentinel and Auxiliary Data

The mapping pipeline was based on temporal metrics calculated on high resolution Sentinel and auxiliary datasets that were accessed, processed and exported at 10m spatial resolution via Google Earth Engine (GEE). In particular, we employed all available S1 data spanning from 2019 to 2022 and all available surface reflectance (L2A) S2 data of less than 80% cloud cover of the same period. S2 pixels affected by clouds or cloud shadows, as well as saturated or defective pixels, were excluded from further processing based on the Scene Classification (SCL) band. The temporal metrics for all data were calculated over two time-periods: dry season (15th May - 1st September) and wet season (15th November - 15th March). To choose the specific temporal windows for the two seasons we consulted with the rainfall estimates of the University of Reading TAMSAT group [10].

For the S2 data, the mean, standard deviation, 10th and 90th percentile metrics were calculated for seven S2 spectral bands, i.e., Blue, Green, Red, Red-Edge (Band 5), NIR, SWIR 1 (Band 11), SWIR 2 (Band 12) and three spectral indices, i.e., NDVI, MSAVI2 and the newly developed dry bare-soil index (DBSI) [11]. For the S1 data, we calculated the same temporal metrics for the HH and HV bands, as well as for their ratio (HH/HV). We also included a number of grey-level co-occurrence textural metrics (GLCM) that have been proven efficient in similar studies [5], [12], [13]. In particular, we calculated the Correlation, Entropy and

Dissimilarity over two different size windows, i.e., 3x3 and 5x5 on the mean images of the HH, HV and HH/HV layers.

Additionally, we employed some ancillary datasets from the GEE Data Catalog, containing bioclimatic and soils information for the selected time periods. More specifically, we included precipitation accumulation, minimum and maximum temperature from the TerraClimate dataset [14] and averaged actual evapotranspiration and interception from the WAPOR dataset [15]. Soil water content information was derived from the OpenLandMap dataset [16] corresponding to soil water content at 33kPa (field capacity) at 10, 30 and 100 cm depth, while soil organic carbon values at 0-20 and 20-50 cm depths, were extracted from the iSDAsoil dataset [17].

2.4. Fractional Woody Cover Mapping

Predictive models were generated using the RF regression algorithm and various combinations of data from different sensors and seasons. All models were individually tuned using 5-fold cross validation to identify the ideal parameterisation for the number of trees and the minimum number of samples for a leaf node. Water bodies, man-made surfaces (e.g., roads, villages, dams, mines) and intensively cultivated land (e.g., commercial orchards, commercial pivot irrigated), were excluded from the mapping analysis, based on the respective categories of the South African National Land-Cover (SANLC) 2018 map [18].

3. RESULTS

We experimented with all possible combinations between data and seasons to create regression models for FWC mapping, resulting in more than a hundred experimental set ups. In order to assess the contribution of each dataset to the regression accuracy, we present and discuss here the performance of a series of experiments that contain a gradually-increasing number of features/predictors.

Figure 1. R^2 rates for S2 and combined S2, S1 and auxiliary (Aux) data experiments.

Achieved rates of coefficient of determination (R^2) and Root Mean Square Error (RMSE) metrics clearly demonstrate that S2 data outperform their C-band S1 SAR counterparts. In particular, when using only S1 features, i.e., the S1 polar band metrics (SI_b) on their own or with the S1 texture metrics (SI_{b_t}), the R^2 did not exceed 69%, and that applies to any season or a combination of both. On the other hand, experiments that included the S2 data, resulted in R^2 rates of $>73\%$, even for the simplest set-up of using solely the S2 band metrics ($S2_b$) for one season (Figure 1).

Interesting remarks for the contribution of different seasons and sensors can be derived from Figure 1. As expected, when using metrics from a single season, best results are achieved with the dry season metrics. For all presented set-ups, using both dry and wet season metrics resulted in the highest R^2 rates. The inclusion of S2 spectral indices along with the spectral bands ($S2_{b_i}$) had no significant improvement on the regression accuracy, as opposed to appending the auxiliary data (Aux) that clearly raised the R^2 rates. Another interesting point is that including the Aux metrics to the S2 datasets had a more positive impact to the regression accuracy than including the S1 metrics. Incorporating data from all seasons and sensors resulted into high regression rates of $>80\%$.

Table 1. RMSE rates for the single and combined season and sensor experiments.

Predictors	RMSE		
	Wet	Dry	Wet & Dry
<i>S1 (+ Aux)</i>			
S1_b	19.88	20.26	19.13
S1_b+Aux	17.47	17.46	17.06
S1_b_t	18.53	18.69	17.95
S1_b_t+Aux	17.29	17.15	16.86
<i>S2 (+ Aux)</i>			
S2_b	16.35	15.55	15.07
S2_b+Aux	15.22	14.67	14.28
S2_b_i	16.35	15.54	14.99
S2_b_i+Aux	15.22	14.72	14.32
<i>S1+S2 (+ Aux)</i>			
S1_b+S2_b	15.44	15.12	14.79
S1_b+S2_b+Aux	14.73	14.37	14.21
S1_b_t+S2_b_i	15.24	14.95	14.70
S1_b_t+S2_b_i+Aux	14.68	14.40	14.25
Best	14.12		

Similar remarks can be drawn by examining the RMSE rates for the S1, S2 and combined experiments in Table 1. Lower error rates per row are marked with bold and underline the outperformance of combining seasons for all set-ups. Green filled boxes mark lower error rates per column and highlight that combining S1, S2 and Aux data provided the best regression results, even without the incorporation of S2 indices and S1 textural metrics, in addition to the S2 spectral and S1 polar band metrics.

Figure 2. Fractional woody cover map for the study area located in Kagisano-Molopo of South Africa.

From all our experiments, the best performance (*Best*) was documented at an R^2 rate of 80.52% for a set up that included the S2 spectral bands and the auxiliary metrics ($S2_{b_i+Aux}$) from all seasons, as well as the polar band metrics (SI_b) from the dry season only. This regression model was used to generate FWC predictions for the whole area (Figure 2).

4. DISCUSSION & CONCLUSIONS

In this work we targeted the accurate FWC mapping on a South African savannah while assessing the contribution of S2, S1 and ancillary bioclimatic and soils data. As a first step, we produced FWC samples from a VHR RGB dataset, following a similar approach with [2], [4], but achieving higher accuracy rates of $>94\%$. FWC results and analysis documented that the presented pipeline achieved high regression rates of $>80\%$ for the all-data and all-season combined experiments. These rates are in most cases higher than those in similar studies applying optical or/and SAR satellite data [2], [4], [5], [12], [19]. This is quite remarkable especially when considering that our mapping is performed at a higher-than-usual spatial resolution (10m), since it has been documented that regression accuracy decreases with pixel size [4], [5].

Regarding the influence of seasonality and the contribution of S1 and S2 metrics in FWC mapping, our results are generally in agreement with similar studies: best single season results were achieved for the dry period and optimal results when combining both seasons, while S2 only

models clearly outperformed the S1 ones. An interesting outcome from the incorporation of ancillary bioclimatic and soils data was that such information was proven to be more beneficial to the S2-based models than if S1 metrics were included. This is an important finding with regards to the computational cost and processing complexity that the inclusion of S1 metrics entails. Our results and overall evaluation can provide important insights in the ongoing efforts for improved mapping, monitoring and assessment of savannah vegetation, which remain one of the least studied biomes, globally.

5. ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This work has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the 2019 Marie Skłodowska-Curie Individual Fellowships grant agreement SAV-EO No 894403.

6. REFERENCES

- [1] A. M. Abdi, M. Brandt, C. Abel, and R. Fensholt, "Satellite Remote Sensing of Savannas: Current Status and Emerging Opportunities," *Journal of Remote Sensing*, vol. 2022, Jun. 2022, doi: 10.34133/2022/9835284.
- [2] E. Symeonakis, A. Korkofigkas, G. Vamvoukakis, G. Stamou, and E. Arnau-Rosalén, "Deep Learning Monitoring of Woody Vegetation Density in A South African Savannah Region," *Int. Arch. Photogramm. Remote Sens. Spatial Inf. Sci.*, vol. XLIII-B3-2020, pp. 1645–1649, Aug. 2020, doi: 10.5194/isprs-archives-XLIII-B3-2020-1645-2020.
- [3] L. Luvuno, R. Biggs, N. Stevens, and K. Esler, "Woody Encroachment as a Social-Ecological Regime Shift," *Sustainability*, vol. 10, no. 7, Art. no. 7, Jul. 2018, doi: 10.3390/su10072221.
- [4] T. P. Higginbottom, E. Symeonakis, H. Meyer, and S. van der Linden, "Mapping fractional woody cover in semi-arid savannas using multi-seasonal composites from Landsat data," *ISPRS Journal of Photogrammetry and Remote Sensing*, vol. 139, pp. 88–102, May 2018, doi: 10.1016/j.isprsjprs.2018.02.010.
- [5] E. Shafeian, F. E. Fassnacht, and H. Latifi, "Mapping fractional woody cover in an extensive semi-arid woodland area at different spatial grains with Sentinel-2 and very high-resolution data," *International Journal of Applied Earth Observation and Geoinformation*, vol. 105, p. 102621, Dec. 2021, doi: 10.1016/j.jag.2021.102621.
- [6] C. Karakizi, Z. Kandylikis, A. D. Vaiopoulos, and K. Karantzalos, "Joint Land Cover and Crop Type Mapping Using Multi-temporal Sentinel-2 Data from Various Environmental Zones in Greece," in *The International Archives of the Photogrammetry, Remote Sensing and Spatial Information Sciences*, Copernicus GmbH, Jun. 2021, pp. 319–326. doi: 10.5194/isprs-archives-XLIII-B3-2021-319-2021.
- [7] "Kagisano-Molopo Local Municipality Five Year Integrated Development Plan - 2017/2018 – 2021/2022." 2022. Available: https://lg.treasury.gov.za/supportingdocs/NW397/NW397_IDP%20Final_2022_Y_20211108T113710Z_tshego_mothibi.pdf
- [8] A. Dayaram et al., "Vegetation Map of South Africa, Lesotho and Swaziland 2018: A description of changes since 2006," *Bothalia*, vol. 49, no. 1, Oct. 2019, doi: 10.4102/abc.v49i1.2452.
- [9] L. Joseph and L. Devadas, "Detection of Rooftop Regions in Rural Areas Using Support Vector Machine," 2015. Available: <https://www.semanticscholar.org/paper/Detection-of-Rooftop-Regions-in-Rural-Areas-Using-Joseph-Devadas/fea266505c46f8bebe01ac593c0dd303c04c9dc55>
- [10] R. I. Maidment et al., "A new, long-term daily satellite-based rainfall dataset for operational monitoring in Africa," *Sci Data*, vol. 4, no. 1, Art. no. 1, May 2017, doi: 10.1038/sdata.2017.63.
- [11] A. Rasul et al., "Applying Built-Up and Bare-Soil Indices from Landsat 8 to Cities in Dry Climates," *Land*, vol. 7, no. 3, Art. no. 3, Sep. 2018, doi: 10.3390/land7030081.
- [12] L. Naidoo, R. Mathieu, R. Main, K. Wessels, and G. P. Asner, "L-band Synthetic Aperture Radar imagery performs better than optical datasets at retrieving woody fractional cover in deciduous, dry savannas," *International Journal of Applied Earth Observation and Geoinformation*, vol. 52, pp. 54–64, Oct. 2016, doi: 10.1016/j.jag.2016.05.006.
- [13] E. Symeonakis, T. P. Higginbottom, K. Petroulaki, and A. Rabe, "Optimisation of Savannah Land Cover Characterisation with Optical and SAR Data," *Remote Sensing*, vol. 10, no. 4, Art. no. 4, Apr. 2018, doi: 10.3390/rs10040499.
- [14] J. T. Abatzoglou, S. Z. Dobrowski, S. A. Parks, and K. C. Hegewisch, "TerraClimate, a high-resolution global dataset of monthly climate and climatic water balance from 1958–2015," *Sci Data*, vol. 5, no. 1, Art. no. 1, Jan. 2018, doi: 10.1038/sdata.2017.191.
- [15] FAO, WaPOR database methodology: Version 2 release, April 2020. Rome, Italy: FAO, 2020. doi: 10.4060/ca9894en.
- [16] T. Hengl and S. Gupta, "Soil water content (volumetric %) for 33kPa and 1500kPa suctions predicted at 6 standard depths (0, 10, 30, 60, 100 and 200 cm) at 250 m resolution." *Zenodo*, Dec. 05, 2019. doi: 10.5281/zenodo.2784001.
- [17] T. Hengl et al., "African soil properties and nutrients mapped at 30 m spatial resolution using two-scale ensemble machine learning," *Sci Rep*, vol. 11, no. 1, Art. no. 1, Mar. 2021, doi: 10.1038/s41598-021-85639-y.
- [18] M. W. Thompson, "South African national land-cover (SANLC) 2018," Department of Environmental Affairs, South Africa; Department of rural development and land reform. Available: https://www.dffe.gov.za/projectsprogrammes/egis_landcover_datases
- [19] K. Wessels, R. Mathieu, N. Knox, R. Main, L. Naidoo, and K. Steenkamp, "Mapping and Monitoring Fractional Woody Vegetation Cover in the Arid Savannas of Namibia Using LiDAR Training Data, Machine Learning, and ALOS PALSAR Data," *Remote Sensing*, vol. 11, no. 22, Art. no. 22, Jan. 2019, doi: 10.3390/rs11222633.